

Elliptic Curves- New Approach to Lenstra's Factorization method

Abstract:

Elliptic Curve Cryptography is a public key cryptography that is used for effective implementation in the field of Cryptography. They are also used in several integer factorization algorithms that have applications in Cryptography. In this paper provides brief introduction of the proposed Algorithm, elliptic Curves over real numbers applied the new approach of the points on the Elliptic Curve by using Lenstra Factorization method.

KeyWords: Number Theory, Cryptography, Elliptic Curve Cryptography, Elliptic curves, Elliptic Curve Factorization method.

Introduction:

Cryptography is the method of protecting information and communications through the uses of codes so that only those for whom the information is intended can read and process it. The history of Cryptography is long and interesting it had very considerable turning point when two researchers from Stand ford and White field Diffie and Martin Hellman published the paper "New Directions in Cryptography "in 1976, they preface the new idea of public key Cryptography.

Providing equivalent level of security with smaller key size is an advantage of ECC compared to RSA.it is very efficient to implement ECC. ECC obtains lower power consumption and faster computation. It also gains small memory and bandwidth because of its key size length such attributes are mainly fascinating inn security applications in which calculative power and integrated circuit space are limited. Wireless devices and smart cards are presenting a good example for the constrained devices with limited resources. Cryptography companies such as Certicom Corporation have already implementing ECC in their products for some commercial purposes which are RFID and Zigbee.This company has an agreement with NSA on a set of cryptographic algorithm called Suite B. This suit uses Elliptic curves and works over the prime field.

The use of Elliptic curve cryptography was first proposed by Neil Koblitz and victor Miller in1985.They did not invent a new Cryptographic Algorithm but they implemented certain existing algorithms using Elliptic Curve Arithmetic. Since ECC studied a lot in the Academic world. The use of ECC in Cryptography is very inviting because of shorter key lengths that can be used in the case of Conventional Cryptography i.e RSA.As par as Cryptography is concerned Elliptic curves has been used for factoring and primality proving.

1 Mathematical part of Elliptic Curve Cryptography over Real numbers:

Definition of elliptic curves: Elliptic curves are not ellipses. They are called this because they are described by cubic equations, similar to those used for calculating the circumference of an ellipse. In general, an elliptic curve is the set of solutions of an equation of the form

$$y^2 + a_1xy + a_3y = x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_4x + a_5 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where the coefficients a_i are elements of some field (R, Z or Z_p) which satisfy some Simple conditions in order to avoid singularities. Such an equation is said to be Cubic, or of degree 3, because the highest exponent it contains is 3. The Eq.1 is Called Weierstrass equation. Also included in the definition of any elliptic curve is a single element denoted O and called point of infinity or the zero point An elliptic curve over real numbers may be defined as the set of points (x,y) which satisfy an elliptic curve equation of the form:

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b, \text{ where } x, y, a \text{ and } b \text{ are real numbers.}$$

Each choice of the numbers a and b yields a different elliptic curve. For example, $a=1$ and $b=1$ gives the elliptic curve with equation $y^2 = x^3 + x + 1$; the graph of this curve is shown below:

If $x^3 + ax + b$ contains no repeated factors, or equivalently if $4a^3 + 27b^2$ is not 0, then the elliptic curve $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$ can be used to form a group. An elliptic curve group over real numbers consists of the points on the corresponding elliptic curve, together with a special point O called the point at infinity.

Figure:1

Elliptic Curve ($y^2 = x^3 + x + 1$)

2 Point addition: Elliptic Curve Addition: A Geometric Approach:

$P + Q = R$ is the additive property defined geometrically.

Elliptic curve groups are additive groups; that is, their basic function is addition. The addition of two points in an elliptic curve is defined geometrically.

The negative of a point $P = (X_1, Y_1)$ is its reflection in the x-axis: the point $-P$ is $(X_1, -Y_1)$. Notice that for each point P on an elliptic curve, the point $-P$ is also on the curve.

Adding distinct points P and Q :The resulted point of adding two different points on the elliptic curve is computed as shown below in figure 2

When $P = (X_1, Y_1)$ and $Q = (X_2, Y_2)$ are not negative of each other,

$(X_1, Y_1) + (X_2, Y_2) = (X_3, Y_3)$; where $X_1 \neq X_2$

$P + Q = R$ where

$$\lambda = (Y_2 - Y_1) / (X_2 - X_1)$$

$$X_3 = \lambda^2 - X_1 - X_2 \text{ and}$$

$$Y_3 = -Y_1 + \lambda (X_1 - X_3)$$

Note that λ is the slope of the line through P and Q .

Figure 2.1

Point Addition:

Suppose that P and Q are two distinct points on an elliptic curve, and the P is not -Q. To add the points P and Q, a line is drawn through the two points. This line will intersect the elliptic curve in exactly one more point, call -R. The point -R is reflected in the x-axis to the point R. The law for

addition in an elliptic curve group is $P + Q = R$.

Shows how a point can be doubled graphically on the elliptic curve. Suppose we want to double a point P on the elliptic curve. A tangent line to the curve and passing by P is taken to double the point. The line must cross the curve through another point; the point is noted as -R. Then we reflect the point -R in the x-axis to the point R where $R=2P$.

The line through P and -P is a vertical line which does not intersect the elliptic curve at a third point; thus the points P and -P cannot be added as previously. It is for this reason that the elliptic curve group includes the point at infinity O. By definition, $P + (-P) = O$. As a result of this equation, $P + O = P$ in the elliptic curve group. O is called the additive identity of the elliptic curve group; all elliptic curves have an additive identity.

Point P and the Negative of P from by definition, $2P=O$ for such a point P if anyone wanted to find $3P$ in this situation, one can add $2P+P$ this becomes $P+O=P$ thus $3P=P, 4P=O, 5P=P, 6P=O, 7P=P, \dots$

Figure

2.2.

To add a point P to itself, a tangent line to the curve is drawn at the point P. If y_P is not 0, then the tangent line intersects the elliptic curve at exactly one other point, -R. -R is reflected in the x-axis to R. This operation is called doubling the point P; the law for doubling a point on an elliptic curve group is defined by:

$$J+J=2L.$$

Figure 2.3

Elliptic curves over real numbers:

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \quad \text{with} \quad a=9, b=-2$$

Mathematics in ECC over finite fields:

Cryptographic operation on Elliptic curve over finite fields are done using the coordinate points of the Elliptic curve.

Elliptic curve over finite fields is of the form $y^2 = \{x^3 + ax + b\} \text{mod } \{p\}$ certain formulas are defined with the points

Figure 1 (a) point addition: (b) doubling: (c) point at infinity y coordinates are 0: (d) point at infinity when the coordinates are mirror image of each other.

1.1 Point addition

The two points $P(x_1, y_1)$ and $Q(x_2, y_2)$ are distinct $P+Q=R(x_3, y_3)$ is given by the following calculations.

Figure 1(a) shows graphical representation of point addition operation

$$\lambda = P\{(y_2 - y_1)/(x_2 - x_1)\}$$

$$x_3 = \lambda^2 - x_2 - x_1 \text{ and}$$

$$y_3 = -y_1 + \lambda(x_1 - x_3)$$

Point doubling

The two points $P(x_1, y_1)$ and $Q(x_1, y_1)$ overlap $P+Q=R(x_3, y_3)$ is given by the following validation

Fig 1(b) shows the representation of point doubling operation.

$$(x_1, y_1) + (x_2, y_2) = (x_3, y_3)$$

Where $y_1 \neq 0$

$2P=R$ where

$$\lambda = 3x_1^2 + a/2y_1$$

$$x_3 = \lambda^2 - 2x_1$$

$$y_3 = \lambda(x_1 - x_3) - y_1$$

Point multiplication:

Let P be any point on the elliptic curve multiplication operation over P is defined by the repeated addition.

$$kP = P + P + P + P + \dots k \text{ times}$$

Point at infinity

If $x_1 = x_2$ and $y_1 = y_2 = 0$ or $x_1 = x_2$ and $y_1 = -y_2$ the points is said to be intersect at infinity denoted by O

Figure 1(c) and 1(d) shows graphical representation of point at infinity.

Finding inverse modulo

For finding inverse modulo using Extended Euclidean algorithm

The GCD of two integers can be found by repeated applications of the division algorithm

$$y^2 = x^3 + 2x + 4 \text{ mod } 7$$

It has the following co-ordinate points $\{(O, (0,2), (0,5), (1,0), (2,3), (2,4), (3,3), (3,4), (6,1), (6,6)\}$

Q	R_1	R_2	R	T_1	T_2	T
2	7	3	1	0	1	-2
3	3	1	0	1	-2	7

Where

Q=Quotient for R_1 divided by R_2

R_1 =Modulus value initially followed by left shift of value from previous R_2R in later cases.

R_2 =Denominator value initially followed by left shift of value from previous R in the later case.

R =Remainder of R_1 divided by R_2

$T_1 = 0$ initially followed by left shift previous value from T_2

$T_2 = 1$ initially followed by right shift of previous value from T .

$T=T_1-Q*T_2$

Continue till $R=0$, and inverse modulo is given by the value at T_2 .

$\lambda = -1 * -2 \pmod{7}$

$\lambda = 2$.

2.Literature review:

Many authors are exploited the applications, strengths and implementations of various tasks of Public Key Cryptography like authentication, digital signature, key agreement and encryption. Neil Koblitz explains about the elliptic curves over finite fields for public key cryptosystems along with him Alfred Menezes and Scott Vanstone extended the idea of discrete Logarithmic problem used in public key Cryptography of Diffie –Hellman to ECC. In his book explained various concepts of Cryptographic Protocol and implementing issues. Lawrence-C-Washington wrote a book called “Elliptic Curves: Number Theory and Cryptography. It provides proofs to many theorems to understand elliptic curves. Terriho gave a very clear example of implementation of ECC-DH key exchange, ECC encryption, elliptic curve digital signature using Mathematics. S.Maria Celestin and K.Muneswaran implemented text cryptography by using ECC by first transforming the message in ASCII values from ASCII value times the generator Sarvana Sunetha and Chandrasekhar design a method to communicate with multiple parties securely non-repudiatively in authentic way of using parallel field multiplier.

Motivation: Many authors implemented encryption and Decryption using ECC have used the ASCII value of the character to

produce affine elliptic curve coordinates by performing point multiplication operation with generator G and the correspond ASCII value of the character. We have come up with a novel idea where use of multiplication common look up table between the sender and the receiver has been completely removed.

The Lenstra elliptic-curve factorization or the elliptic-curve factorization method (ECM): Lenstra factorization method is a fast, sub-exponential running time algorithm for integer factorization, which employs elliptic curves. For general purpose factoring, ECM is the third-fastest known factoring method. The second-fastest is the multiple polynomial quadratic sieve, and the fastest is the general number field sieve. The Lenstra elliptic-curve factorization is named after Hendrik Lenstra.

Practically speaking, ECM is considered a special-purpose factoring algorithm, as it is most suitable for finding small factors. Currently, it is still the best algorithm for divisors not exceeding 50 to 60 digits, as its running time is dominated by the size of the smallest factor p rather than by the size of the number n to be factored. Frequently, ECM is used to remove small factors from a very large integer with many factors; if the remaining integer is still composite, then it has only large factors and is factored using general-purpose techniques. The largest factor found using ECM so far has 83 decimal digits and was discovered on 7 September 2013 by R. Propper.^[1] Increasing the number of curves tested improves the chances of finding a factor, but they are not linear with the increase in the number of digits.

Working procedure of the proposed Algorithm:

The Lenstra elliptic-curve factorization method to find a factor of a given natural number 'n' works as follows:

1. Pick a random elliptic curve over Z/nZ , with equation of the form $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \pmod{n}$ together with a non-trivial point $p(x_0, y_0) \in Z/nZ$ and then setting $b = y_0^2 - x_0^3 - ax_0 \pmod{n}$ to assure the point is on the curve.
2. One can define Addition of two points on the curve, to define a Group. The addition laws are given earlier in this paper.

We can form repeated multiples of a point $P: [k]P = P + P + P + \dots$ (k times) The addition formulae involve taking the modular slope of a chord joining P and Q and, and thus division between residue classes modulo n , performed using the extended Euclidean Algorithm. In particular, division by some $v \pmod{n}$ includes calculation of the $\gcd(v, n)$.

Assuming we calculate a slope of the form u/v with $\gcd(u, v) = 1$, then if $v = 0 \pmod{n}$ the result of the point addition will be ∞ , the point "at infinity" corresponding to the intersection of the "vertical" line joining $P(x, y), P'(x, -y)$ and the curve. However, if $\gcd(v, n) \neq 1, n$ then the point addition will not produce a meaningful point on the curve; but, more importantly, $\gcd(v, n)$ is a non-trivial factor of 'n'

Compute $[k]P$ on the elliptic curve (\pmod{n}) where k is a product of many small numbers say a product of small primes raised to small powers as in the form $p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} \dots p_r^{a_r}$ in the factorial

$B!$ for some 'n' of too large B . This can be done efficiently one small factor at a time say to get $[B!]P$, first compute $[2]P$, then $[3]([2]P)$ then $[4]([3]P)$ and so on. B is picked to be small enough so that B -wise point addition can be performed in reasonable time. After finish the calculations above without encountering non-invertible elements (\pmod{n}) , it means that the Elliptic curves (modulo primes) order is not smooth

Enough to so we need to try again with a different curve and starting point. The time complexity depends on the size of the numbers smallest prime factors and can be represented by $\exp(\sqrt{2} + O(1)) \sqrt{\ln p} \ln \ln p$

where p is the smallest factor of $n, L_p \left[\frac{1}{2}, \sqrt{2} \right]$.

Working of the Algorithm: If p and q are two prime divisors of n , then $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \pmod{n}$ implies the same equation also modulo p and modulo q . These two smaller elliptic curves with the $+$ $=$ -addition are now genuine groups. If these groups have N_p and N_q elements, respectively, then for any point P on the original curve, by Lagrange's theorem, $k > 0$ is minimal such that $kP = \infty$ on the curve modulo p implies that k divides N_p ; moreover, $N_p P = \infty$. The analogous statement holds for the curve modulo q . When the elliptic curve is chosen randomly, then N_p and N_q are random numbers close to $p + 1$ and $q + 1$, respectively (see below). Hence it is unlikely that most of the prime factors of N_p and N_q are the same, and it is quite likely that while computing eP , we will encounter some kP that is ∞ modulo p but not modulo q , or vice versa. When this is the case, kP does not exist on the original curve, and in the computations we found some v with either $\gcd(v, p) = p$ or $\gcd(v, q) = q$, but not both. That is, $\gcd(v, n)$ gave a non-trivial factor of n .

ECM is at its core an improvement of the older p -1 algorithm. The $p - 1$ algorithm finds prime factors p such that $p - 1$ is b -power smooth for small values of b . For any e , a multiple of $p - 1$, and any relatively prime to p , by Fermat's little theorem we have $a^e \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Then $\gcd(a^e - 1, n)$ is likely to produce a factor of n . However, the algorithm fails when $p - 1$ has large prime factors, as is the case for numbers containing strong primes, for example.

ECM gets around this obstacle by considering the group of an elliptic curve over the finite field Z_p , rather than considering the multiplicative group of Z_p which always has order $p - 1$.

The order of the group of an elliptic curve over Z_p varies (quite randomly) between $p + 1 - 2\sqrt{p}$ and $p + 1 + 2\sqrt{p}$ by Hasse's theorem, and is likely to be smooth for some elliptic curves. Although there is no proof that a smooth group order will be found in the Hasse-interval, by using heuristic probabilistic methods, the Canfield-Erdos-Pomerance theorem with suitably optimized parameter choices, and the L -notation, we can expect to try $L[\sqrt{2}/2, \sqrt{2}]$ curves before getting a smooth group order. This heuristic estimate is very reliable in practice.

Performance Comparison:

To factorize choose the prime number $n = 455839$. Let choose the Elliptic curve $y^2 = x^3 + 5x - 5 \pmod{n}$ with point $P = (1, 1)$ on it then to compute $10!P$ The slope of the tangent line and some point $A = (x, y)$ is $s = 3x^2 + 5/2y \pmod{n}$

using s we can calculate $2P$ if the value of s is of the form a/b where $b > 1$ and $\gcd(a,b)=1$ then to find the modular inverse of b , if it does not exist then $\gcd(n,b)$ is a non-trivial factor of n .

So first compute $2P$ i.e $2P=(x^1, y^1)$ $x^1 = s^2 - 2x = 14$ and $y^1 = s(x - x^1) - y = 4(1 - 14) - 1 = -53 \pmod{n}$

Then to compute $3(2P)$ there $s(2P)$

i.e $s(14, -53) = -593/106 \pmod{n}$ using Euclidean Algorithm $455839 = 4300 \cdot 106 + 39$ then $106 = 2 \cdot 39 + 28$ then $39 = 28 + 11$ then $28 = 2 \cdot 11 + 6$ then $11 = 6 + 5$ then $6 = 5 + 1$, hence $\gcd(455839, 106) = 1$ and so on.....

The points on the curve are given below

$P(1,1)$

$2P(14,455786)$

$3P(364134,180099)$

$4P(259851,116255)$

$5P(151721,188012)$

$6P(1796885,427131)$

$7P(109678,196782)$

$8P(102407,127974)$

$9P(125856,241367)$

$10P(71712,258327)$

These points all on the curve.

The same points calculation for large prime with the help of programing code using Python

Python Code for point generation:

```
# https://asecuritysite.com/encryption/ecc_points_mult
import sys
import libnum

a = 5
b = -5
p = 455839 # prime number
n = 10 # number of points to show
x = 1 # starting point

# y^2 = x^3 + ax + b (mod p)
print("a=", a)
print("b=", b)
print("p=", p)
print("n=", n)
print("x-point=", x)

if (n > 455839): n = 455839

z = (x**3 + a * x + b) % p
if (libnum.has_sqrtmod(z, {p: 1})):
y = next(libnum.sqrtmod(z, {p: 1}))

print("P\t(%d,%d)" % (x, y), end='')
```

```

if ((y**2 % p) == ((x**3 + a * x + b) % p)): print(" \tPoint is on curve")
else:
print(" \tPoint is not on curve")
sys.exit()

```

```

s = ((3 * x**2) + a) * libnum.invm(2 * y, p)

```

```

x1 = (s**2 - 2 * x) % p

```

```

y1 = ((s * (x - x1)) - y) % p

```

```

x3 = x1
y3 = y1
x2 = 0
y2 = 0
counter = 1

```

```

for i in range(2, n + 1):
counter = counter + 1
if (counter > n): sys.exit()

```

```

print("%dP\t(%d,%d)" % (counter, x1, y1), end=' ')
if ((y1**2 % p) == ((x1**3 + a * x1 + b) % p)):
print(" \tPoint is on curve")

```

```

rtn = libnum.invm(x1 - x, p)
if (rtn == 0):
print("%dP=0" % (counter + 1))
counter = counter + 2
s = ((3 * x**2) + a) * libnum.invm(2 * y, p)

```

```

x1 = (s**2 - 2 * x) % p

```

```

y1 = ((s * (x - x1)) - y) % p
print("%dP\t(%d,%d)" % (counter, x, y), end=' ')
if ((y**2 % p) == ((x**3 + a * x + b) % p)):
print(" \tPoint is on curve")

```

```

else:
s = (y1 - y) * rtn

```

```

x2 = (s**2 - x1 - x) % p

```

```

y2 = ((s * (x1 - x2)) - y1) % p

```

```

x1 = x2
y1 = y2

```

```

a= 5
b= -5
p= 455839
n= 10
x-point= 1
P (1,1) Point is on curve
2P (14,455786) Point is on curve
3P (364134,180099) Point is on curve
4P (259851,116255) Point is on curve
5P (151721,188012) Point is on curve
6P (179685,427131) Point is on curve
7P (109678,196782) Point is on curve
8P (102407,127974) Point is on curve
9P (125856,241367) Point is on curve
10P (71712,258327) Point is on curve

```

Conclusion:

In this given paper we have implemented a new technique to perform text cryptography using ECC.

The order of the group of an elliptic curve over \mathbb{Z}_p varies (quite randomly) between $p + 1 - 2\sqrt{p}$ and $p + 1 + 2\sqrt{p}$ by Hasse's theorem, and is likely to be smooth for some elliptic curves. Although there is no proof that a smooth group order will be found in the Hasse's-interval, by using heuristic probabilistic methods, the **Canfield-Erdos-Pomerance** with suitably optimized parameter choices, and the L -notation, we can expect to try $L[\sqrt{2}/2, \sqrt{2}]$ curves before getting a smooth group order. This heuristic estimate is very reliable in practice.

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